

OPTIMUM REINFORCEMENT OF METALLIC MATRIX

BY DISCONTINUOUS FIBERS

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Abstract

While considering A.Kelly's equation for tensile strength of composites with metallic matrix reinforced by fibers with length which is larger than the critical one the influence of the scale factor is taken into account which significantly affects brittle fibers strength. Here it is shown that the maximum strength of a composite with brittle fibers is achieved by reinforcement of it by fibers with the length equal to about the critical one. The difference between the maximum strength of a composite and strength of a composite reinforced by fibers of critical length is negligible. The composite having the maximum strength has some value of plastic elongation up to failure, its value increases with decrease in coefficient of Weibull distribution of fibers.

Simple and reliable equations for calculation of tensile strength of a composite consisting of metallic matrix and discontinuous fibers were reviewed by A.Kelly [1]:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m^* (1 - V_f) + \sigma_f [1 - K(1 - \eta)] V_f \quad (1)$$

when $l_f \geq l_{cr}$ and

$$\tilde{\sigma}_c = \sigma_m (1 - V_f) + \frac{\tau_m l_f}{d_f} V_f \quad (2)$$

when $l_f < l_{cr}$,

where σ_c , σ_f and σ_m - tensile strength of a composite, fiber and matrix, respectively; σ_m^* - stress in the matrix at the moment of the composite fracture; V_f - volu-

me fraction of fibers; η - const $\approx 0,5$; l_f - fiber length; $K = l_{cr}/l_f$, where l_{cr} is determined from equation

$$l_{cr} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_f d_f}{2\tau_m} \quad (3)$$

Here d_f and τ_m are fiber diameter and the ultimate shear strength of the matrix, respectively. (It is supposed, that the shear strength of the bond between fiber and matrix is no less than the ultimate shear strength of the matrix).

According to equation 1 the fracture mechanism of a composite is determined mainly by breaking fibers. Therefore, elongation of the composite up to breaking is equal to one of the fibers up to breaking.

The stress in a fiber is less than its strength at any elongation of matrix if a fiber length is less than the critical one. Therefore, breaking of composite is a result of matrix breaking at the stress equal to tensile strength of the matrix, $\bar{\sigma}_m$. Elongation of the composite up to its failure is approximately equal to elongation of the unreinforced matrix up to its failure. This mechanism is determined by equation (2).

Strength of brittle materials is well described by the Weibull distribution and depends on the scale factor according to equation (2):

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1(V_1)}{\bar{\sigma}_2(V_2)} = \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1}\right)^{1/\beta} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_1(V_1)$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2(V_2)$ - average values of tensile strength of brittle material with volumes V_1 and V_2 respectively and β - Weibull's coefficient of strength distribution defined from the equation

$$\mu \approx \beta^{-0,92} \quad (5)$$

where μ - the variation coefficient of material strength. Equation (4) for fibers with constant cross section can be written as

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_1(l_1)}{\bar{\sigma}_2(l_2)} = \left(\frac{l_2}{l_1}\right)^{1/\beta} \quad (6)$$

where l - fiber length.

Now, considering $l_2 = l_{cr}$ in equation (6) and putting it into equation (3) we shall get equation for determining the critical length of fiber in which influence of the scale factor is taken into account:

$$l_{cr} = \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_f(l_1) \cdot l_1^{1/\beta} \cdot d_f}{2\tau_m}\right)^{\beta/1+\beta} \quad (7)$$

This equation has a universal meaning. It can be used

for calculation of l_{cr} both for plastic fibers characterized by large value β of coefficient β which at first approximation may be considered to be infinite and for brittle fibers where the coefficient varies in the range from 2 up to 6. In case when $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, equation (7) transforms to equation (3). While increasing β from 1 to ∞ , l_{cr} is monotonously reduced from

$$\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_f(e_f) \cdot e_f \cdot d_f}{2T_m} \right)^{1/2} \text{ to } \frac{\bar{\sigma}_f(e_f) \cdot d_f}{2T_m} \quad (\text{Fig. I}).$$

Let us transform equation (I) considering that the tensile strength of the fiber, $\bar{\sigma}_f$, is a function of its length, i.e. $\bar{\sigma}_f = \bar{\sigma}_f(l_f)$. We shall have:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m^* (1 - V_f) + \bar{\sigma}_f(e_f) \left(\frac{e_f}{e_m} \right)^{1/\beta} \left[1 - \frac{1}{2l_f} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_f(e_f) \cdot e_f^{1/\beta} \cdot d_f}{\sigma_m} \right)^{1+\beta} \right] V_f \quad (8)$$

where l_f - base length of a fiber on which the average value of its strength $\bar{\sigma}_f(l_f)$ is determined.

Now, let's examine the influence of the fiber length on the ultimate strength of a composite, σ_c .

For example we shall take a hypothetical composite consisting of the ductile matrix ($\sigma_m = 50 \text{ kg/mm}^2$; $\sigma_m^* = 15 \text{ kg/mm}^2$) and brittle fibers ($d_f = 0,1 \text{ mm}$, $\bar{\sigma}_f(l_f) = 300 \text{ kg/mm}^2$; $l_f = 20 \text{ mm}$; $V_f = 0,5$). Here for simplification we suppose that σ_m^* does not depend on l_f and is equal to 30 kg/mm^2 ; $\bar{\sigma}_f(l_f)$ is considered to be constant and independent of β . As experimental data [3] have shown, in practice, increase of β coefficient is inevitable connected with $\bar{\sigma}_f(l_f)$ reduce for the same type of fibers.

Fig.2 illustrates that the maximum value of composite strength, σ_c^{max} , is achieved not at the infinite fiber length according to equation (I), but at l_f^{max} near to l_{cr} which is given by

$$l_f^{max} = l_{cr} \frac{\beta+1}{2} \quad (9)$$

The maximum tensile strength of the composite reinforced by brittle fibers is given by

$$\sigma_c^{max} = \sigma_{max}^* (1 - V_f) + \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_f(e_f) \cdot e_f^{1/\beta} \cdot d_f}{\sigma_m} \right)^{1+\beta} (1+\beta) \right]^{-1/\beta} \bar{\sigma}_f(e_f) \cdot e_f^{1/\beta} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\beta} V_f \quad (10)$$

It is obvious, that the difference, $\Delta \sigma_c$, between σ_c^{max} and σ_c^{cr} (the tensile strength of a composite with critical length of fibres) monotonously rises with increasing β (Fig.2). $\Delta \sigma_c$ increases from 0 when $\beta = 1$ to $\bar{\sigma}_f(l_f) V_f$ when $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ (Fig.1). The range of changing fiber length in which composites tensile strength is

higher than the tensile strength of composites reinforced by fibers of critical length simultaneously rises from 0 to ∞ .

Both tensile strength and plasticity of a composite are of great importance for technology. Elongation of the composite with brittle continuous fibers is negligible and equal to elongation of fibres up to their breaking.

Composites with discontinuous fibers, the length of which is less than l_{cr} , have maximum plasticity. While changing fiber length from the critical value and higher plastic elongation of the composite monotonously reduces from maximum (which is equal at first approximation to plastic elongation of the unreinforced matrix) to zero at some definite length of fiber.

We can get the equation for determination of σ_m^* from equation (7) putting $l_{cr} = l_f$ and $2\tau_m = \sigma_m^*$ into it

$$\sigma_m^* = \frac{\bar{\epsilon}_f(l_f) \cdot e^{n\beta} \cdot d_f}{l_f^{1+\beta/\beta}} \quad (II)$$

From common equation of tension curve of matrix material, $\sigma_m = \sigma_m^y + K \epsilon^n$, we have that plastic elongation of matrix ϵ_m^* which is equal to about ultimate plastic elongation of the composite corresponds to the stress σ_m^* . The higher is n , the maximum value of which is 1, the larger is plastic elongation of the composite at constant l_f .

Therefore composites with maximum strength achieved at $l_f = l_f^{max}$ are also characterized by plastic elongation which is the larger, the less is coefficient β and n .

We get different combinations of ultimate tensile strength and ultimate plastic elongation of composite by changing the fiber lengths in the range from l_f^{max} to l_f^{cr} for the given couple of matrix and fibers materials. In this case σ_c will vary from σ_c^{cr} to σ_c^{max} and the plastic elongation vary accordingly from ϵ_m (maximum) to ϵ_c^* corresponding to σ_c^{max} . The region of changing these three values is shown on Fig.2 by dash lines.

Table I summarizes calculated values of characteristic parameters for the hypothetical composite. Here we suggest that the matrix tension curve in its plastic region is described by parabola with $n = 1/2$. While calculating values of $\sigma_m^*(l_f^{max})$ corresponding to definite value of l_f^{max} we have used modification of equation (II) which now is written as

$$\sigma_m^*(l_f^{max}) = \frac{2\tau_m}{\left(\frac{\beta+1}{2}\right)^{1+\beta/\beta}} \quad (I2)$$

Equation (12) clearly shows that $\sigma_m^*(l_f^{\max})$ depends only on matrix strength and coefficient β .

Table I.

β	l_{cr} mm	l_f^{\max} mm	$\sigma_m^*(e_{f2}^{\max})$ kg/mm ²	σ_c^{cr} kg/mm ²	σ_c^{\max} kg/mm ²	$\Delta\sigma_c$ kg/mm ²	ε_c^* %	ε_c^{cr} %
2	1,93	2,89	27,4	266	277	11	25	20
3	1,44	2,88	19,8	205	225	20	2,5	20
4	1,21	3,02	15,9	176	199	23	<1	20
6	0,99	3,47	11,6	149	177	28	0	20

It is seen from the table that in case of composite maximum strength it is possible to provide some part of composite plasticity. This inevitably increases fracture energy and long service life of material in constructions.

Conclusions

1. The maximum strength of composite reinforced by brittle fibers can be achieved providing that the metallic matrix is reinforced by fibers the length of which is equal to 1,5-3,5 l_{cr} .
2. Difference between the maximum strength and strength of composite with critical length of fibers is not large. It will be preferable to use composites with fiber length equal to about critical one, since they have the ultimate elongation equal to about the ultimate elongation of matrix in structures.
3. Composites with maximum strength have a certain value of elongation.

References

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2. W.Weibull. "A Statistical Theory of the Strength of Materials", Ing.Vetenskaps.Acad.Hande (Roy Swedish Inst.Eng.Research Proc.), 1939, No 151.
3. I.L.Svetlov, V.G.Lutzau, T.I.Bulygina, V.F.Gasilov. "Mashinovedenie", 1975, No 1.

Fig.I. Dependence of the composite tensile strength, σ_c , on the fiber length, l_f , at various values of β .

Fig.2. Influence of coefficient β on:
 1 - $\Delta\sigma_c$; 2 - l_{cr} .

QUESTION: O.B. Pedersen, Danish Atomic Energy Commission, Risø

Professor Chawla, in your present work on thermal cycling of copper-steel I understand that you observe wedge type voids which you attribute to the operation of a Zener mechanism. However, in a previous work on copper-tungsten I believe that you found evidence for the reverse mechanism, whereby grain boundary sliding takes place as a result of void formation. Do you have an explanation of this apparent difference in the behaviour of the two systems?

ANSWER: K.K. Chawla, Instituto Militar de Engenharia, Rio de Janeiro

The answer to this question is given partially in the text. I should like to add that in the work referred to (ref. 2 above) I used 5-nine pure copper and rather large grain size (~ 2 mm) where in conditions similar to a low stress creep test would prevail and one would expect r-type cavities. Too, the interfiber spacing was much greater in Cu/W work⁽²⁾ which gave a much steeper thermal stress gradient (and, therefore, a much steeper vacancy gradient) than in the present work which appeared to result in void formation first then sliding. Hence, the absence of r-type voids in the present work at low cycling temperatures.

QUESTION: A. Berghezan, University of Louvain, Belgium

Do you observe in these systems the familiar cellular structure forming different colonies as they are normally observed in eutectics?

ANSWER: L.R. Wolff, Laboratorium voor Fysische Chemie, Eindhoven

As I described in my paper, I indeed observed what I call "Eutectoid Duplex Cellular Growth (E.D.C.G.)" in some of these ternary and quaternary systems. Just as in eutectics, these cells originate from the lamellar growth, which is more or less perpendicular to the curved interface.

The curved interface develops as a result of the difference between the composition of the high temperature phase and the gross composition of the low temperature phases into which it decomposes. This causes the high temperature phase to change in composition,

but a different composition implicates a different growth rate at the same temperature. So if the transformation rate is lowered by the change in the high temperature phase composition, the interface will be curved. Cells will then be formed with the (at least for eutectics) now familiar featherlike morphology.

QUESTION: O.N. Carlson, Max Planck Inst. fur Metall-Forschung, Stuttgart

Have you done any irradiation studies on ferritic steel composites? If so, are void formation, creep data available on those?

ANSWER:

Yes, we have. Ferritic steels were chosen in first instance to reduce the high temperature irradiation embrittlement. The irradiation we have made showed that indeed this embrittlement was reduced by at least a factor five in comparison with austenite steels. We have only one result of void swelling experiment in a fast reactor: at 575°C and $5 \cdot 10^{22}$ n/cm² (>0.1 MeV) the measured density decrease is less than 0.2%. Simulation experiment in a H.V.E.M. showed, if not a complete absence of voids, a much reduced swelling rate compared to austenite steels. The results of the test now in progress in different fast reactors will not be available before mid '76.

An experiment to measure the irradiation induced creep is in preparation and it will be put in the reactor end of 1975.

QUESTION: S.J. Harris, University of Nottingham, UK

After being subjected to high temperature creep tests why do these composites embrittle at room temperature? Is there a relationship between creep temperature and degree of embrittlement (at ~20°C)?

ANSWER: W.C. Harrigan, The Aerospace Corp., Los Angeles

The embrittlement of the composite when tested at room temperature after creep testing is related to the "creep" process. We envision the macroscopic straining that takes place during creep is caused by fiber alignment due to creep of the aluminum matrix. The embrittlement is probably caused by diffusion of the TiB interface into the Al matrix and formation of complex AlTiB phases. Since this is a diffusion process, it is indeed temperature dependent.

QUESTION: K.N. Street, Ecole des Mines de Paris, Corbeil, France

Did you conclude that the carbon fibres themselves were creeping and that your apparent composite creep was not simply due to matrix relaxation and/or fibre breakage?

ANSWER: W.C. Harrigan

This question was answered partially in the previous answer. Because of the low stress dependence and low activation energy, we conclude that we are not observing true creep of the fibers. Any of a number of matrix controlled mechanisms are probably operating. However the creep response of the system is still quite good.

QUESTION: J. Rexer, Battelle, Geneva

Do you think that Al-C can be competitive with Al-B for high temperature long time applications, taking into consideration that for Al-C the compatibility problem will be much more severe because of the higher specific interface and therefore the much quicker fibre degradation?

ANSWER: W.C. Harrigan

In the aluminum-graphite system, I am talking about fibers that are protected by a TiB interface that is reasonably stable up to 400°C. I do not have enough information to date to fully assess how Al-C will compete with Al-B. Indications are that the Al-C system up to 400°C will have a higher normalized creep rupture stress for 1000 hour failure than present Al-B systems. For example, the 1100 Al-Thornel 50 composite (Fig. 3) has a 1000 hr creep rupture stress that is 70% of the room temperature tensile strength. Typically, Al-B Composites have 1000 hour creep rupture stress at 400°C that are 50% of the room temperature tensile strength.

QUESTION: E. Foster

Do other property differences exist between B/Al composites of 6061 and 1100 alloys?

ANSWER: H.H. Grimes, NASA-Lewis Research Center, Cleveland, Ohio

In response to your question I would briefly mention the recent work of H. Grimes and R. Lad on thermal cycle fatigue. We have tested composites of these alloys from near room temperature to 320 and 420°C for up to 3000 cycles. Both 5.6 and 8 mil B composites were used. Our findings indicate no significant degradation of longitudinal UTS of unidirectional composites at 320°C, but increasing degradation of strength to about 130 KSI at 420°C. This degradation could not be accounted for by equivalent time at temperature. The strength low, however, was essentially the same for the two alloys used despite obvious differences in interface bonding and fracture characteristics.

QUESTION: Mr. MacDonald

You evidently see a change in the fatigue fracture surface as the

applied stress is increased. Would you describe why this occurs and the importance of it? (I assume this is the fatigue crack portion and not the final fracture portion of the fracture surface.)

ANSWER: M.F. Amateau, The Aerospace Corp., Los Angeles

The change in appearance of the fatigue surface as the applied stress is increased is undoubtedly due to the change from plane strain to plane stress conditions. The importance of this is that the mechanism of matrix fracture dictates the fracture mode in the composite.

QUESTION: S.J. Harris, University of Nottingham, UK

Under low stress-high cycle conditions does matrix induced fibre fatigue take place in aluminium alloy - 30% graphite fibre composite?

ANSWER: M.F. Amateau

The question of whether matrix induced fatigue in graphite fibers occurred during the low stress cycling was not explicitly determined in these experiments. Metallographic sections through the fracture revealed no fiber fractures ahead of the matrix cracks. Comparisons of the fatigue life of the fibers themselves with that of the fibers in the composite were not made in this study. Indeed, the degree of scatter that such data is likely to possess would tend to render the value of such comparisons questionable. Experiments are now in progress to examine the rate of propagation of a crack through a center-cracked-sheet specimen. The area ahead of the crack will be monitored for fiber breadage. Estimates of the breaking stress based on fracture mechanics may supply a more definitive answer to your question.

QUESTION: Mr. Hieber, Philips Research Lab, Hamburg

Electroplated Ni must be much more temperature sensitive with respect to recovery and columnar grain recrystallization than the hot pressed nickel. What are the aging conditions (temperature-time characteristics) of both composites and the structural degradations?

ANSWER: H. Takeda, Tokyo Shibaura Electric Co., Kawasaki-City

In electroplated Ni/sapphire composite X-ray diffraction profile changed during the heat cycle. At the first heating X-ray diffraction profiles were not suitable for stress measurement because the profiles were very broad and indicated preferred orientation due to electroplating. After the first heat cycle, the X-ray diffraction profiles were sufficient to measure stresses. However, high level stresses were not found during next heat cycle. We have not determined the reason whether due to electroplated Ni characteristics or debonding at the interface.

In hot pressed Ni/sapphire composite X-ray diffraction profile did not change during several heat cycles.

QUESTION: Mr. Hieber

What is the definition of "bonding strength": 1) spontaneous adhesion loss by not T_{1t} -dependent crack propagation or 2) long term stability related to the creep tests?

ANSWER: H. Takeda

In this paper, "bonding strength" means rather spontaneous adhesion. In an actual composite, we should use macroscopic bonding strength considering dynamic behavior of the interface.

QUESTION: F. Carpay, Philips Research Labs, Eindhoven, Netherlands

In your 600°C range you mentioned that "impurity diffuses away from the grain boundary." You deduce this from the microstructure. What is the driving force for this diffusion? I believe you turn it around: the mobility of the grain boundary increases with temperature and the impurity is left behind.

ANSWER: K.K. Chawla, Institute Militar de Engenharia, Rio de Janeiro

No, I do not turn it around. Please refer to Fig. 5a of the paper which is a scanning electron micrograph in the compositional contrast mode. The black spots are the agglomerated impurities. Remember that when a grain boundary migrates it leaves behind an impression of its original position. Notice that the impurities on the left hand side of the picture do not lie where the original grain boundary lay. On the other hand, in the right hand side of the picture one can see a glob of impurities on the grain boundary and one can also see that, as pointed out in the text, this glob acts as restraining agent for the grain boundary and has prevented the migration of a segment while the rest of the boundary has migrated away. At such high temperatures ($>0.5 T_m$), with a great ease of diffusion, it is not unknown that impurities may diffuse away from the grain boundaries, segregation of impurities is lost and grain boundary diffusivity increases. I might cite a very recent work of D. Gupta and R. Rosenberg at IBM Thomas J. Watson research center (Thin Solid Films, 25 (1975) 172) in support of this.

The following questions were addressed to R. Signorelli, NASA Lewis Research Center, Cleveland.

QUESTION: M.R. Piggott, University of Toronto

Are the results obtained by Dr. Signorelli and the results by Dr. Street for toughness agreed with the Piggott formula:

$$\text{Fracture surface energy: } \frac{V_f d \sigma_{fu}^3}{12 E_f \tau_i}$$

where V_f : volume fraction
 d : fiber diameter
 σ_{fu} : strength
 E_f : modulus of the fibers
 τ_i : interfacial shear stress

ANSWER:

The variables included in the Dr. Piggott formula were not systematically varied since these were not model system studies to relate toughness with failure modes. Most variables included were held constant. However the increase in toughness with diameter was in agreement with the formula. Increased bonding of 1100 aluminum matrix composites increased impact strength. This might imply that increased interfacial shear stress values increased rather than decreased toughness.

QUESTION: J. Dolowy, DWA Composite Specialities, Inc.

With regard to your observation of "tougher" B-Al using a less well bonded system with an 1100 matrix, could the same effect be seen with the 6061 matrix if it was intentionally not well bonded (as Tetelman hypothesized several years ago).

ANSWER:

The improved impact strength of the 1100 Al matrix composites was not related to less-well bonded composites. In fact, blade-like specimens which were hot-pressed twice to increase bonding showed higher impact resistance. Plastic deformation rather than fiber pull-out was the energy absorption mechanism that we concentrated on. Additional energy absorption mechanisms can be studied to investigate further increases in metal matrix composite impact properties.

QUESTION: W.B. Hellig, General Electric R & D Center

How do polymer composites compare with metal-matrix composites in regimes where both can operate?

ANSWER:

The higher density of metals is compensated by improved performance

for some applications because of properties such as modulus, ductility, toughness, erosion resistance and moisture and radiation tolerance. Further, fabrication of metal matrix composite components can be simpler, quicker and cheaper than both monolithic metal and polymer matrix composites. Thus application of both polymer and metal matrix composites for specific components should be evaluated objectively to determine which results in a greater benefit.

COMMENT: E. Scala, Consultant, Cortland, New York

An advantage of metal-matrix composite processing is the lower capital equipment cost (and competitive availability) for fabrication compared to titanium alloy blades.

QUESTION: S. Isserow, AMMRC

Which titanium alloy was used for the matrix in your studies and to what extent, if any, was the choice of the Ti alloy determined by compatibility with the fiber or other matrix properties such as composite performance and ductility?

ANSWER:

Standard titanium alloys have been used for most studies, with Ti-6 Al-4 V being selected most frequently. There is a need to select matrix alloys to obtain the performance sought. It is reasonable to expect that matrix alloy selection will be influenced by this need as the focus of R&D shifts from exploratory and feasibility studies to component application.

QUESTION: W.R. Hoover, Sandia Labs

Why did you choose energy absorbed in a Charpy test as a screening test rather than a test which measures the load carrying capability of the composite such as a fracture mechanics test which gives K_{IC} .

ANSWER:

As mentioned in this paper, the data obtained were not limited to Charpy tests. A variety of tests with varying velocity of impact, mass of the projectile and specimen size and shape were performed. Further, simulated service tests including engine ground and flight tests are underway or planned. This is a normal progression of evaluation used in the application of new materials to gas turbine engines.

QUESTION: J.D. Buckley, NASA-LRC

Considering the variability in lots of composite materials, how many specimens did your line graphs represent, did the data points

a mean or least squares fit, and how wide was the test band on either side of the line (fracture toughness) curves?

ANSWER:

The exact quantitative values obtained for each test condition was not the issue in the programs described, particularly when up to a tenfold increase in impact strength was obtained. The main point made was that significant increases in impact strength were possible and the trends and relative effect of the main variables has been well substantiated by tests with specimens from more than one source, tested at different laboratories.

COMMENT: A. Berghezan, University of Louvain, Belgium

(Ré : Paper by K.S. Nair): The approach used by the authors to increase both the strength of the fibres and the matrix is very interesting.

However, during the aging the matrix will become more brittle or has lower ductility. Therefore, I suggest to test these composites under Charpy impact testing to see whether the toughness is or is not affected.

QUESTION: A.P. Levitt, AMMRC

I noted in the 4 March 1975 issue of Commerce Business Daily that a contract had been issued to Pratt and Whitney Aircraft to fabricate B/Al fan blades for the F-111 engine. Does this mean that the FOD characteristics of B/Al have been improved to acceptable levels, and what is the Al matrix?

ANSWER: K. Prewo, United Aircraft Research Labs

The F-111 blades are third stage, non-FOD-critical components fabricated from a 6061 matrix plasma sprayed tape precursor, and the blades will be flown.

COMMENT: W.C. Harrigan, The Aerospace Corp., Los Angeles

In our aluminum-graphite composite studies, creep data were obtained on wire and fatigue data on a pressed product. 6061 fatigue data were obtained on individually pressed bars and 202 fatigue data on plate material.

QUESTION: K. Prewo

What is the form of the creep curves, and what are the creep strain rates?

ANSWER: W.C. Harrigan

The creep curve has a small primary stage (approximately 0.3%) followed by a steady state behavior to fracture at between 0.5 and 1% strain. Creep strain rates are between 10^{-8} and 10^{-5} per minute.

QUESTION: H. Lilholt, Danish AEC

Were the fibers long and were they creeping? The low stress exponent is probably indicative of creep controlled by matrix creep.

ANSWER: W.C. Harrigan

The fibers were continuous and at the stresses and temperature involved, the matrix probably crept to relaxation and carried no load. I agree that matrix controlled creep was indicated.

QUESTION: H. Lilholt

Is it clear why the 606/composite at 350°C showed a high stress exponent, and what was the stress exponent of the pure 606/Al alloy?

ANSWER: W.D. Harrigan

The higher stress dependence has something to do with diffusion and hence creep in the composite. The stress exponent varied between 6.7 in composites above $0.75 T/T_s$ and 20 below this temperature.

COMMENT: L.W. Davis, NETCO, Long Beach

Properties of composites in the steel-aluminum system are dependent first on the type of wire employed. Piano wire obtains its high properties from cold work and will lose those properties when exposed to molten Al at a rate dependent on the processing parameters of that particular lot of wire. If stainless steel wire is used, the properties in the composite will be directly in accord with the rule of mixtures and there will be different sets of properties depending on whether the Al alloy is in the annealed condition, the -T4 heat treated condition, the -T6 condition, or the -T6 condition followed by 2 to 5% cold work for stress relief. This results in the highest strength values.

Discussion by A. BERGHEZAN of the paper presented by Robert A. SIGNORELLI, entitled : "METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR AIRCRAFT PROPULSION SYSTEMS", Session III B, (Geneva and Boston)

It was extremely interesting to hear Dr. SIGNORELLI speaking about the progresses made at NASA, in both the fabrication methods of several high performance metal-matrix composite materials, as well as in the studies made in view of their application to advanced aircraft propulsion systems.

More precisely, I was interested to hear about the successful preparation, via press-bonding and rolling of W-wires/superalloy matrix composites, which are seriously considered for application to turbine blades for high temperature use (up to 1100-1150°C).

In this connection, I would like to recall that these very same composites have also been prepared in Brussels at the Union Carbide European Research Labs, some 3 years ago. The incorporation of the W-fibres into the alloy matrices has been performed exclusively in solid-state, namely by co-extrusion.

Why extrusion ?

Extrusion creates an intimate contact between the components of the composite which, coupled with the necessary high-pressure to force simultaneously the components through the die, appeared likely to promote easier diffusion bonding. Bonding is further enhanced by the newly created surfaces which form necessarily during the coextensive flow which the components undergo during the process.

Extrusion has some other interesting advantages : in spite of the fact that it operates in the solid state which appears essential to avoid the excessive diffusion it also gives the advantages of the matrix phase to fill completely the empty spaces between the fibres and/or fibres and matrix. This makes it possible to use any geometrical cross-section of fibres and any stacking sequence. This is a very substantial advantage as the common commercial wires always have round cross-section and even the best packing of this geometry leaves an empty space of 10% of volume. To fill tightly this empty volume with a protective matrix is an absolute requirement for such reactive fibres as the refractory metal wires.

The high reduction ratio which is possible with extrusion is another additional interesting advantage. This allows one to introduce the reinforcing wires with large diameters (e.g. 1 mm Ø), which are much easier to handle, to pack and to obtain after extrusion much finer fibres with enhanced mechanical properties.

Finally, the extrusion temperature can often be kept under the recrystallization temperature of fibres which when recrystallized

become brittle, such as Be and W. The recrystallization of W-fibres even in the absence of any diffusion suffices to induce poor impact properties in the final composite at low and room temperature and also an appreciable and erratic loss of strength as shown by Dean ¹⁾ on his W-containing composites prepared by liquid phase infiltration above the recrystallization temperature of the W-reinforcing fibres.

The first co-extrusions ²⁾ showed that one can obtain with this method a perfect bonding between the components as demonstrated by the theoretical reinforcement obtained on the extruded composites ³⁾. There remained, however, to find a more practical method for a uniform distribution of the fibres in the matrix which should also insure their perfect alignment, as that used originally where the fibres were, one by one, put in place by hand, aligned and maintained in position during incorporation.

Such a method has been conceived and applied to the preparation of refractory metal reinforced stainless steel and various superalloys ⁴⁾.

A simple method of precise alignment and uniform distribution of fibres in a metal matrix

The method has been developed in three variants :

a) In a first variant, it consists of winding a continuous row of reinforcing fibres within a foil of matrix material. It is similar to the winding of chopped tobacco inside a paper foil to form a cigarette.

Winding is carried out on a lathe around a core which can be chosen at will either of matrix or of the reinforcing material. The winding leads to a spiral pattern of the matrix sheet which maintains inside it a second spiral of reinforcing fibres (Figs. 1 and 2).

In this variant, the continuous row of reinforcing fibres has to alternate with fibres of the matrix in order to separate each of the reinforcing fibres. This method requires therefore the availability of both reinforcing fibres and fibres of the matrix to be used. In the case where fibres of the matrix are not available (as for most superalloys) and in order to avoid the additional expense of making fibres, a second variant was developed.

b) The second variant consists of regularly folding in a zig-zag pattern a foil of the matrix. Reinforcing fibres are then placed to fill the valleys of the folded zig-zag pattern. A plane sheet of the matrix material is placed over the reinforcing wires. Then the sandwich is turned over and reinforcing fibres are placed in the opposite valleys of the folded foil. Another plane sheet of the matrix is placed over this. This 5 layer "unit" can either be wound in a spiral or several layers can be packed on top of each other to form a sandwich of multiple layer units.

This variant solves cheaply the problem of lack of matrix wires which are thus no longer required. It is also much simpler than other recently developed methods which require grooving of the matrix sheet on both sides by selective etching after having marked the position of the grooves by photo-resist imaging on a special initial coating of the matrix sheet.

An astonishing precise alignment and uniform distribution of fibres in the matrix can be obtained with both variants of the method (Figs. 3, 4 and 5).

c) The third variant is the simplest : two foils, one of matrix and the second of reinforcing material are exactly superposed. The double layer ribbon is then wound around a core on the lathe. The resulting pattern is a double spiral structure which leads to a new type of reinforcing material (Figs. 7 and 8).

In practice, all three variants appear handy and precise in achieving perfect alignment and uniform distribution and are hence suitable to be applied on a production scale. Further, the method appears to be astonishingly versatile as it permits the incorporation of any kind of fibre in a metal matrix : rigid wires, flexible metallic or glass filaments, ceramic fibres, carbon filaments, etc. It also permits incorporation of any volume fraction desired and the fabrication of the composite in various shapes, e.g. either round bars or plane sheets.

The method described was tested by using different "off the shelf" materials by which several high performance composites were prepared.

Fig. 6 shows the difference between the strength of matrix and the reinforced composite at 1100°C. ^{5, 6)}

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Response to Discussion of Session IIIB

The work described by Professor Berghezan is a valuable contribution to the effort to develop refractory fiber/superalloy composites. The solid-state co-extrusion process described in the discussion can be advantageous for composite fabrication. We also have used co-extrusion for high temperature composite fabrication in our work at NASA-Lewis Research Center and similar techniques have been used by others in the production of beryllium/titanium composites. The Co-Extrusion process produces a multilayer composite with essentially uniaxial fiber orientation. Production of monolayer tape by solid state rolling of a fiber array between two sheets of alloy foil is a similar fabrication process designed to yield composite sheet which can be readily fabricated by secondary diffusion bonding into angle-ply components for applications where uniaxial fiber composites are less desirable.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

4

MECHANICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

GENEVA

K.N. Street, Chairman
S.T. Mileiko, Co-Chairman

BOSTON

K.N. Street, Chairman

KEY SPEAKER

B.W. Rosen

SELECTED PAPER

T. Hayashi

RAPPORTEUR

H. Lilholt, Geneva
N.J. Pagano, Boston

CHAIRMAN'S SUMMARY REPORT

Session 4

by K. N. Street
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In setting the stage most adequately for the session, the Key Speaker B. Walter Rosen emphasized the complexity and uniqueness of composite structures and the dangers of attempting to fit such materials into classical molds. This latter tendency remains even today a real one as the art and science of composites must evolve largely as the product of scientists, engineers and designers whose background encompasses the behaviour and application of homogeneous isotropic materials. Failure itself must be redefined in many cases and dissociation of experimental data from the physical aspects of, for example, fracture can result in misleading notions.

Time dependent alterations in the initial "defect" population within a composite structure can in certain circumstances amount to progressive damage or wearout as discussed by Rosen. In other cases, residual properties are enhanced and we may describe this as a form of progressive "healing". Related phenomena, although of chemical rather than mechanical origin, are well known in many natural composites such as wood and bone. Further research in this area with man-made composites and interaction of researchers of different disciplines may well yield rewarding results.

Taking the simple but widely utilized structural member of a tube, Professor Hayashi in his Selected Paper provided the session with an excellent detailed account of the factors dictating the optimum design of composite tubes from a strength and rigidity standpoint. As composites find their way into more applications, increasing attention will have to be directed towards the long term properties under complex loading conditions of tubular members.

It is perhaps noteworthy that for the slower developing metal matrix composites, the first major application consists of Boron-Aluminum tubes in the Space Shuttle.

The session papers were well balanced in so far as geographical origin was concerned, half from North America and half from Europe and elsewhere. Except for one paper on thermoelastic properties and one on the difficult question of the nature of fiber-matrix interfaces, the principal theme in the works was fracture and toughness. Some of the major questions left unanswered included what is self-similar crack growth in these macroheterogeneous materials wherein the fibers may be 150 μm in diameter and of variable strength and the interfiber spacing similarly large? Even if only as a stop-gap engineering tool, can classical fracture mechanics methods be widely adopted or modified to yield meaningful fracture criteria? The evidence presented in the papers on the effects of notches on the static, fatigue and impact behaviour of composites clearly indicates the formidable problems which face us today in this field.

Although the fatigue strength of composites tends in most systems to be good compared to unreinforced materials, the precise mechanisms of fatigue damage initiation and multiple-direction and hence multiple mode crack propagation remain to be resolved in many cases. One could envisage for a given composite material, widely different fatigue damage mechanisms depending upon the state of the fiber-matrix interface, the defect structure of the matrix resulting from the fabrication procedures, the fiber spacing and degree of perfection of alignment, the mode of sollicitation and the environment. As mentioned earlier, fatigue "healing" can also occur, particularly when notches are present.

Perhaps due to experimental difficulties, the creep behaviour of composites remains little-studied even though the potential of composites as load bearing members at elevated temperature is particularly attractive. It was encouraging to find some preliminary experimental results in the present session as this field at the present time possesses an overabundance of the theoretical and model studies but only one or two complete experimental works.